

A Study on Job Stress and Employee Performance in Afghanistan's Banking Sector

Sadat Said Redwan^{1*}, Batoor Omaree¹, Sher Bano¹

¹ College of Economics and Management, Taiyuan University of Technology

Accepted August 17, 2021

Published August 23, 2021

*Corresponding Author:

Sadat Said Redwan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5236745>

Pages: 71-80

Funding: None

Distributed under

Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Said Redwan, S., Omaree, B., & Bano, S. (2021). A Study on Job Stress and Employee

Performance in Afghanistan's Banking Sector. *North American Academic Research*, 4(8), 71-80.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5236745>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

1. Overview

1.1 Introduction

Stress is frequently misunderstood and misinterpreted, which leads to avoidable issues. It is therefore critical to have a thorough understanding of stress before attempting to manage it. Over time, the definition of stress has evolved. Initially, it was thought to be a result of the environment, and then it was thought to be a result of the person's own strain. Stress is a psychological and physical state that occurs when an individual's resources are insufficient to cope with the situation's demands and pressures. As a result, stress is more likely in some situations and in some people than in others. Stress is defined as a person's reaction to a demand

ABSTRACT

Employee health and well-being, as well as an organization's productivity and profits, have all been shown to be negatively impacted by workplace stress. Job stress can be caused by a lack of ability to meet job demands, job insecurity, mismatch with job profile, and relationships with coworkers, and other organizational factors. In today's fast-changing environment, employees face high levels of work stress, greater frustration, and higher job expectations. Individuals and businesses can take steps to lessen the negative effects of work stress. Employees, on the other hand, must learn to recognize the signs of stress, and employers must be aware of the negative effects stress has on both their employees' health and the bottom line. This paper investigates the impact of work stress on employee performance in the banking industry. The study's sample came from the banks of Kabul, Afghanistan's capital. To collect relevant primary data, a structured questionnaire was used. The end result revealed that work stress causes subjective reactions in employees such as fear, anger, and anxiety, resulting in poor mental health. Based on these findings, it was suggested that banks reduce mental stress, clear role ambiguity, and job insecurity by redesigning jobs, as well as organizing counseling sessions and workshops on stress management for employees.

Keywords: JOB STRESS; AFGHAN BANKING SECTOR; EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

placed on them. It's simply defined as "a state in which one experiences a gap between one's current and desired state." Stress is defined by Merriam Webster as a physical, chemical, or emotional factor that causes bodily or mental tension and may be a cause of disease. When the brain detects a threat, it has a natural reaction.

Furthermore, Kahn and Byosiere investigated the effects of role conflict, role ambiguity, and work overload on job stress. Work-family conflict, according to Al., can lead to job stress. Such factors always have a negative psychological and physical impact on employees. Job stress has become a major challenge for organizations as a result of the massive amount of it. As a result, job stress has a significant impact on employee behavior today. Employees are the most important assets for the organizations, and they cannot be treated like machines because of their significant role in running them effectively and successfully. Employees who work in a stress-free environment are clearly more productive and prove to be valuable assets for an organization; however, when organizations fail to address their employees' stress, this leads to increased absenteeism, turnover, ineffective work, and, in most cases, legal financial damages.

As a result, the implications drawn for understanding workplace stress are explored in this article. The notions of job stress, as well as reasons for job stress such as role conflict, role ambiguity, work overload, and work-family conflict, will be examined in the following literature review.

1.2 Problem Statement

Most organizations that want to increase productivity end up overburdening employees with work in order to meet deadlines, which can have negative psychological and physical effects on employees and lead to outcomes that are counter to what these organizations want to achieve. Although companies are paying more attention than in the past to the effects of the trauma their employees experience when they place unreasonable demands on them, there is still room for improvement. To generate enough revenue to be self-sustaining and to be able to fund the purchase of modern equipment, efficient service provision and resource allocation were required once again.

2. Research Literature

2.1 Literature Review

The purpose of this article is to go over the research on the effects of stress on job performance. As a result, it is critical to review the impact of stress on the human body, which affects their job performance, as well as a review of the literature on the impact of stress on employee job performance.

The majority of the articles reviewed by this researcher mentioned the impact of stress, but many of them only discussed the impact of stress on specific aspects or dimensions of the job, indicating that the researcher has yet to come across any article or report that takes a comprehensive approach to the subject. As

a result, it's critical to understand what constitutes job performance, as well as the various aspects of a job that are likely to be affected by stress.

Job performance, according to Scullen, is divided into four categories: general performance, human performance, technical performance, and administrative performance. Job performance, according to Rubina, is the result of three factors working together: skill, effort, and the nature of work conditions. Employees' skills include their knowledge, abilities, and competencies; effort refers to how motivated they are to finish the job; and the nature of work conditions refers to how accommodating these conditions are in facilitating their performance. Organizations are primarily concerned with the performance of their employees, regardless of factors or circumstances. Employee performance leads to organizational performance, which is a measure of their success. An organization's ultimate success or failure is largely determined by the performance of its employees.

Stress has a significant impact on company and individual performance, as well as having a negative impact on employee health. Employee well-being and job satisfaction are negatively related to the sources of stress that we refer to as Occupational Stress Inducers (OSI) in this study, according to studies conducted in western countries. In their study on the impact of stress on teaching faculty performance, discovered a negative relationship between organizational structure and employee efficiency, whereas rewards were found to be positively correlated with employee efficiency, as expected.

Workload, role conflict, and insufficient monetary reward, according to Usman, are the primary causes of employee stress, which leads to decreased employee efficiency. Productivity, Job Satisfaction / Morale, Absenteeism, Decision Making Abilities, Accuracy, Creativity, Attention to Personal Appearance, Organizational Skills, Courtesy Cooperation, Initiative Reliability, Alertness, Perseverance, and Tardiness, accordingly, are all aspects of employee job performance that are likely to be affected by stress.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Method

Quantitative research method is used for primary data collection in this research. A paper- and-pencil self-administered questionnaire technique is chosen due to the nature of the research and the measurement scales chosen. In order to ensure anonymity and eliminate interviewer bias, standardized questions were designed. Percentage Analysis method was used to analyze and interpret results and achieves research objectives.

Percentage Analysis method was used to analyze and interpret results and achieves research objectives. The variable used to for analyzing was Independent Variable relating to employee performance and Dependent Variable relating to job stress

The empirical data was collected in the late March, simultaneously in all the banks in order to avoid potential bias due to the different number of employees and work load. The three listed bank to be used for data collection is as follows

1. Bank Millie Afghan
2. Pushtany Bank
3. Afghanistan International Bank

3.2 Selection of Case Study

The following three banks are the headquarters of each bank so high number employees are working with many department and high number of day to customer. Moreover, since the spring time will be close to financial year closing time, which means that the employees were exposed to more demanding job conditions. The questionnaires were distributed among the employees from certain departments in three banks, which agreed to participate in the research. The banks are situated in one city center in Kabul, Afghanistan, belong to the same Banking service category, however, there are certain differences in the organizational profile of the three banks. Table 1.1 gives an overview of the important details about the three banks that will be involved in the study.

Table 1.1: Overview of the Banks

	Bank Millie Afghan	Pushtany Bank	Afghanistan International Bank
Age of business	10	12	8
Number of Departments	15	12	16
Number of employees	800	400	550
Daily Walk in customer	5000	3500	4000

4. Analysis of Results

4.1 Results and Analysis

Question 1: My educational background is appropriate for my position.

We can see from this data that more than 51% of employees believe their educational background is appropriate for their employment. However, around 13% of respondents from various banks disagree for the

same reason.

Question 2: In my company, there is a dearth of assistance.

We can see that 31% of respondents disagree that there is a lack of assistance in their workplace. As a result, this is not the primary cause of their job stress. However, we cannot overlook the fact that 19% of employees feel this is one of the factors contributing to their poor performance.

Question 3: One of the main sources of my stress is work overload and time constraints.

More than 52% of employees at various institutions are stressed out as a result of job overload and time constraints. This might be a key factor in employee underperformance.

Question 4: Stress levels rise as a result of a lack of social support from coworkers and bad interpersonal relationships.

According to the graph below, roughly 34% of employees do not experience a lack of social support or have poor connections with their coworkers. As a result, this is not the source of their anxiety. However, nearly 8% of employees strongly believe that they suffer a lack of support and bad connections with their coworkers, which causes them significant stress.

Question 5: There is no source of inspiration or encouragement for innovation.

The majority of employees think that their bank encourages innovation and motivation. However, a small proportion of employees believe that they are not sufficiently motivated or encouraged to be creative.

Question 6: In the numerous tasks I do, I am unable to leverage my strengths.

A large majority of employees are able to apply their skills to their work. As a result, individuals are able to perform better and their job stress lessens. However, if we look at the graph, we can see that 25% of employees believe that they are not able to fully exploit their skills.

Question 7: At work, I believe I am undervalued.

This bar graph depicts a good trend in which the majority of employees do not feel undervalued at work. This indicates that their work is respected in their employment, which aids and pushes them to do a good job. This is a major source of stress for nearly 23% of employees who believe they are undervalued at their workplace.

Question 8: Working overtime makes it harder to strike a work-life balance.

Employment-life balance has become a major cause of stress for half of the people here as a result of overtime work. Because they spend so much of their day at work, people in this industry are unable to find a balance between their personal and professional lives.

Question 9: I'd like to make a career move and change industries.

Even after being exposed to such difficult conditions at work, some individuals are adamant about not changing industries or jobs. Only 7% of employees firmly agree that if given the opportunity, they would change jobs and industries.

Question 10: My job is stressful in general.

Overall, 37% of employees are neither fully agreeing nor disagreeing that their job is stressful. As a result, despite the fact that there are a few professional stresses, they are able to manage with them and still desire to pursue a career in the same sector.

5. End Notes

5.1 Recommendations

The goal of this study was to determine the relationship between job stress and employee performance in Mumbai, as well as the factors that influence stress. According to the hypothesis, job stress has a negative relationship with job performance, meaning that when stress occurs, it has a negative impact on employee performance, and that lowering stress increases performance, so the two are inversely proportional. Employees' intentions to perform better in their jobs are reduced by stress in the workplace. As stress levels rise, employees' thinking becomes demoralized, and their willingness to work well decreases. Stress is undoubtedly necessary for improving employee performance, but only to a certain extent. Finally, organizations can change or eliminate stress by redesigning jobs to reduce feelings of undervaluation,

workplace victimization/bullying, unclear roles/errands, work-home interface; fear of joblessness, exposure to traumatic workplace incidents, and economic instability.

5.2 Conclusion

The baking industry has been transformed by technological advancements, and competition has become more globalized as a result of current economic conditions. Employees in the banking sector are also experiencing increasing levels of stress. The results of this study show that there is a link between bank type, gender, age, education, job role, interpersonal relationships, and the impact of occupational stress. As a result, employees in the banking sector should adopt new coping strategies in order to maintain good physical and mental health, which will boost the bank's productivity.

References

1. Ahmed, A. and M. Ramzan (2013) "Effects of Job Stress on Employees Job Performance A Study on Banking Sector of Pakistan." *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* 11(6): 61-68.
2. Alkubaisi, M. M. (2015). "How can Stress Affect Your Work Performance? Quantitative Field Study on Qatari Banking Sector." *Business and Management Research* 4(1).
3. Bashir, U. and M. I. Ramay (2010). "Impact of Stress on Employees Job Performance" A Study on Banking Sector of Pakistan." *International Journal of Marketing Studies* 2(1): 122-126.
4. Basu, S., et al. (2019). "A Study on Stress in Public and Private Sector Bank Employees in West Bengal." *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)* 6(12): 93-97.
5. Elahi, Y. A. and M. Apoorva (2012). "A detail study on Length of Service and Role Stress of Banking Sector in Lucknow Region." *Research Journal of Management Sciences* 1(5): 15-18.
6. Enekewe, C. I., et al. (2014). "Stress Management Techniques in Banking Sectors in Nigeria." *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* 16(7): 33-38.
7. Giorgi, G., et al. (2017). "Work-Related Stress in the Banking Sector: A Review of Incidence, Correlated Factors, and Major Consequences." *Front. Psychol* 8: 1-17.
8. Jayasinghe, C. and M. V. S. Mendis (2017). "Stress and Job performance: A study on banking sector of Northern region of Sri Lanka." *International Journal of Research Publications* 1(1).
9. Khalid, A., et al. (2020). "The Impact of Job Stress on Job Burnout among Bank Employees in Pakistan, With Psychological Capital as a Mediator." *Front. Public Health* 7(1): 1-9.
10. Khan, A. (2015). "Job Stress among Managers in Public & Private Sector Banks: A Case Study of SBI and ICICI Bank." *Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 4(5): 006-013.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

